

Semi-Supervised Learning with Coevolutionary Generative Adversarial Networks

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ABSTRACT

It can be expensive to label images for classification. Good classifiers or high-quality images can be trained on unlabeled data with Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) methods. We use coevolutionary algorithms with Semi-Supervised GANs (SSL-GANs) that work with a few labeled and some more unlabeled images to train both a good classifier and a high-quality image generator. A spatial coevolutionary algorithm introduces diversity into the GAN training. We use a two-dimensional grid of GANs to gain discriminator loss diversity with a distributed cell-level coevolutionary algorithm. The GAN components are exchanged between neighboring cells based on performance and population-based hyperparameter tuning. The approach is demonstrated on two separate benchmark datasets, and with only a few labels, we simultaneously achieve good classification accuracy and high generated image quality score. In addition, the generated image quality and classification accuracy are competitive to state-of-the-art methods.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Semi-supervised learning settings**; **Bio-inspired approaches**; *Neural networks*;

1 INTRODUCTION

Labeling image data is often expensive and time-consuming. Machine Learning (ML) categorizes data as labeled (supervised) or unlabeled (unsupervised). In Semi-Supervised Learning (SSL) ML models are trained with datasets containing some labeled data and the rest is unlabeled [39]. In addition, a Generative Adversarial Network (GANs) can be used for SSL [9, 24]. A GAN estimates the distribution from which real data samples are obtained [14]. The GAN consists of two artificial neural networks (ANNs), a generator that generates data samples from a latent space input and a discriminator which discriminates between generated samples (“fake”) and samples from a dataset (“real”). The objective and loss functions are defined to train the generator to generate a sample that cannot be discriminated from a real sample by the discriminator. GANs: (1) produce realistic data samples due to the adversarial interactions [14]. (2) can use few samples due to their generative nature. Numerous image applications use GANs, e.g. 3D object generation [4], image-to-image translation [30], multispectral and panchromatic images fusion [10], and medical image generation [41]) and data types [22, 25, 46].

GANs are quite difficult to train with gradient based methods, e.g. finding an equilibrium. Training pathologies that cause this

are, e.g. mode collapse [3], discriminator collapse [20], and vanishing gradients [2]. There are some black-box ML algorithms that use evolutionary computation [45] to overcome this when training GANs [8, 40]. For GANs and SSL others apply different loss functions and complex GAN architectures [9, 11, 21, 47]. However, GAN-SSL methods often produce good classifiers or high quality images, but not both good classifiers and high quality images.

Our research questions are: **RQ-1**: Can an evolutionary GAN method train the parameters of both a high-accuracy classifier and a high-quality generative model? **RQ-2**: Can higher quality samples be generated from GANs with some labels (SSL) compared to no labels (unsupervised)?

We combine SSL-GANs with spatial coevolution and gradient-based learning to improve the robustness of GAN training. We extend Lipizzaner [33], which has the evolutionary computation properties, such as training parameter diversity, spatial communication, local (sub-population) selection, plus the evolution of generator ensemble weights and the learning rate under stochastic gradient descent [15]. Lipizzaner results are diverse and can recover from mode collapses [12, 15, 38]. We introduce majority voting classification, spatial diversity loss and balanced label batch sampling to create Lipi-SSL. The experiments for Lipi-SSL are on the MNIST [19] dataset as a proof of concept and the more complex CIFAR-10 [18] dataset. The experiments show that Lipi-SSL can achieve both good accuracy and generated image quality, also in comparison to state-of-the-art (SoA) SSL GAN methods. Our contributions are:

- **Simple SSL GAN for both classification and generation performance**: Our method, Lipi-SSL, trains the parameters of a simple SSL GAN for both classification and image quality with majority voting for classification, spatial diversity loss and balanced label batch sampling.

- **Improved classification accuracies with few labels**: We achieve accuracies of around 96% using only 100 (0.167%) labeled data points for training out of the 60 000 data points in the MNIST training data. We observe even higher accuracies with more labels.

- **Competitive Generated Image Score**: The quality of the generated images is quantified by either the Fréchet Inception Distance [16] or an Inception score [32]. The reported scores for images generated by the Lipi-SSL approach indicate an improved quality compared to some SoA methods.

The paper structure is as follows: background in Section 2, related work in Section 3, method in Section 4, experiments in Section 5, and conclusions in Section 6

2 BACKGROUND

A GAN consists of two neural networks, the generator and the discriminator [14]. The generator learns the features of samples obtained from a “real” data distribution and mimic them to generate “fake” data. The discriminator, learns the features that distinguish a real image from a fake image.

At the beginning of GAN training, the generator produces images from a random vector z drawn from a *latent space*, usually defined as a normal distribution, $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. The discriminator observes real images from the training dataset and fake images from the generator, and tries to discriminate real from fake images. The generator uses this as feedback to update its parameters and generates images from other latent space vectors.

Figure 1: Example of SSL-GAN for MNIST digits generation.

Formally the goal of GAN training is to learn two set of parameters, u and v that approximates and discriminates the real data distribution, G_* . The generator is obtained from a class of generators \mathcal{G} , each characterized by the variables $u \in \mathcal{U}$, while the discriminator is obtained from a class of discriminators \mathcal{D} , each characterised by a variables $v \in \mathcal{V}$. Where $\mathcal{U}, \mathcal{V} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^p$ are the parameter spaces of the generators and discriminators. GANs apply adversarial learning by optimizing their parameters according to a minmax optimization problem defined in Eq. 1

$$\min_{u \in \mathcal{U}} \max_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \mathbb{E}_{x \sim G_*} [\phi(D_v(x))] + \mathbb{E}_{x \sim G_u} [\phi(1 - D_v(x))] \quad (1)$$

The function $\phi : [0, 1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a concave function *measuring function*. The left operand is the probability that when x is taken from the real data distribution (G_*), it is classified as real. The right operand, identifies the data point taken from the generator’s fake data distribution (G_u) as fake. $D_v(\dots)$ corresponds to the probability that the data point is real, which is why in the generator’s loss component we use $1 - D_v(x)$. Thus, GAN training is applied to find the parameters that make the generator to maximize the probability that the discriminator classifies fake images as real ones. The training dataset is unlabeled, so is unsupervised GAN training.

Semi-supervised GANs (SSL-GANs) consider partially labeled datasets [24]. They simultaneously train the generator to produce images and also the discriminator as a classifier, see Figure 1. An SSL-GAN discriminator (trained on a dataset with K classes) outputs $K + 1$ labels. The first K labels are the associated with real images an the $(K + 1)$ th one is the fake label (i.e., \mathcal{F} class in the figure). Thus, the discriminator is penalized for incorrectly predicting a real

or fake image with a the wrong label. Appendix A introduces the softmax loss based method to train SSL-GANs.

3 RELATED WORK

In this section, we present related work on Semi-supervised GANs, Evolutionary GANs and Distributed Evolutionary GAN training

Semi-supervised GANs. Semi-Supervised learning (SSL) aims to reduce the amount of labelled data needed for accurate inference. In SSL models are trained with datasets containing a some labelled data and the rest is unlabelled. SSL GANs simultaneously train the generator to produce images (unsupervised) and both discriminate and classify the generated images(supervised).

For example, Salimans et al. used Feature Matching [32] loss (FM) for the generator, rather than maximization of the modified generator loss [14]. Feature matching performs well theoretically and yields good classification results in practice, the quality of images produced is quite low and can easily be distinguished as fake by humans. Another example of SSL GAN specific loss is triplet loss (TL), in which the input is structured as triplets of a query, a positive example and a negative example. Zieba et al. [47] used the TL as one of the discriminator’s loss components and this resulted in improved classification performance. Finally, Denton et al. introduce Context-Conditional GAN (CC-GAN) [9] which take a different approach with semi-supervised learning using in-painting. They use weights for the supervised and unsupervised loss components.

GAN training has pathologies, e.g mode collapse is a frequently occurring pathology [3], and these occur for SSL GANs as well. For example to work around this issue Salimans et al. propose Minibatch Discrimination (MB D.) [32], where the discriminator looks at multiple points at the same time and the correlation of input samples is provided as input in the intermediate layers.

Another common issue faced by SSL-GANs is that they are limited by the amount of labelled data used. Unified GAN (UGAN) [21] uses good and bad data samples (adversarial examples) to train the classifier of a GAN. A UGAN uses four networks - two generators, one classifier and one discriminator. One generator generates unlabeled data and the other generates labeled data. Another SSL GAN is MarginGAN [11] which was primarily designed to achieve very high classification performance on a dataset while using minimal amounts of labelled data. In addition to a generator and discriminator, a MarginGAN contains a third component, a classifier.

Evolutionary GANs. Evolutionary computation (EC) is a class of population-based optimization algorithms modeled on genetic evolution. EC defines an input (genome) space for individual solutions in a population that are subject: in each iteration (generation) the top individuals are selected from the population and varied, then the new individuals are evaluated and assigned a score (fitness) by an objective function (fitness function). EC has been used to e.g., optimizr the ANN parameters through neuroevolution and evolving ANN architectures [5, 23, 35, 43].

Wang et al. proposed Evolutionary GAN (EGAN) [40]. In each epoch of training, an EGAN uses multiple loss functions, each associated with a generator and evolves a population of generators against a single discriminator by selecting the best performing generator for the next epoch. EGANs introduce diversity through mutation.

Another example is the COEGAN [7, 8] approach which evolves the neural network architectures for Generator and Discriminator and then coevolution is used to train the adversarial components of GANs. Moreover, Evolved GAN applies a genetic algorithm (GA) to evolve the architectures of the generators and discriminators [13]. A cooperative coevolutionary algorithm has also been proposed to conduct adversarial multi-objective optimization [6].

Distributed Evolutionary GAN Training. Coevolutionary algorithms refer to environments where agents are interacting and are trained with different objective functions. Competitive coevolutionary algorithms (CCA) have adversarial populations that simultaneously evolve solutions against each other [27] with individuals engaging in two-player games. They use fitness functions that rate a solution relative to its adversaries, like a minimax optimization. A spatial (2D toroidal) topology can efficiently control the mixing of adversarial populations in coevolutionary algorithms [15, 38]. Studies showed that the spatially distributed competitive coevolutionary GAN training mitigates pathologies [1, 15, 38]. E.g. Lipizzaner, where each cell contains a generator-discriminator pair. Mustangs randomly selects a loss function to train each cell for each generation to increase diversity [36]. The cells allow data decomposition to train GANs in each cell with different subsets of data for data diversity [37]. Finally, distributed GAN training represents a high-dimensional optimization problem with high computational requirements. Lipizzaner maximizes the scalability by running the sub-population training on independent computational resources by applying asynchronous parallelism [15, 26].

In this paper we take advantage of distributed evolutionary GAN training for SSL to use a simple GAN architecture with diverse loss weights to improve classification performance with limited impact of data generation quality. We focus on a simple GAN architecture, with regards to loss functions and ANNs, as well as evolution.

4 METHOD

This section describes the main Lipi-SSL properties and the Lipi-SSL distributed GAN training algorithm.

4.1 Lipi-SSL properties

The Lipi-SSL method extends standard Lipizzaner [15] to apply SSL. Lipi-SSL co-evolves a population of generators $G = \{g_1, \dots, g_N\}$ against a population of discriminators $D = \{d_1, \dots, d_N\}$. The g_i and d_i individuals are based on the ANNs based on Softmax SSL-GAN.

In Lipi-SSL, the individuals in a population are located in each cell of a toroidal grid. Each cell contains a generator-discriminator pair called the *center*. Overlapping Von Neumann neighborhoods are used to form two sub-populations, one of generators (G) and one of discriminators (D), in each cell. (see Figure 2) These sub-populations participate in the CCA training phase to update the *center* (see Algorithm 2). Lipi-SSL uses SSL to optimize the parameters of the ANNs, and the overlapping neighborhoods determine the communication/migration policy of the *best* individual between overlapped cells. During Lipi-SSL training, each cell learns a generative model based on its sub-population of generators and weights for

the mixture, and a classifier ensemble based on its sub-population of discriminators.

Figure 2: Example of Lipi-SSL grid and overlapping neighbors. As example, it highlights the von Neumann neighborhoods of cells 2 and 4. The black bidirectional arrows indicate where the cell’s neighbor is, i.e., the neighbors to the East (right) and North (top) of cell 2 are cells 0 and 8, respectively. In addition, cells 2 and 4 have two overlapping cells (cells 1 and 5) that allow communication/migration (exchange of individuals from the sub-populations) between 2 and 4.

The most distinctive new properties of Lipi-SSL are:

Majority voting classification Lipi-SSL returns a generative model based on an ensemble of generators and a classifier defined by a sub-population of discriminators that apply majority voting. For each batch of images, the predictions of the discriminators are combined (frequency of labels), and the label with the highest frequency becomes the final classification label. This type of image classification ensemble can improve classification accuracy [17].

Spatial diversity loss In SSL-GAN, the discriminator loss function aggregates the unsupervised loss, \mathcal{L}_{Du} , and the supervised loss, \mathcal{L}_{Ds} (see Eq. 5 in Appendix A). Two weight parameters are defined, w_u and w_s , to weigh the importance of \mathcal{L}_{Du} and \mathcal{L}_{Ds} , respectively (see Eq 2).

$$\mathcal{L}_D = w_u \mathcal{L}_{Du} + w_s \mathcal{L}_{Ds}, \quad w_u, w_s \in [0, 1], \quad w_u + w_s = 1 \quad (2)$$

An SSL-GAN with the weights $w_u=1$ and $w_s=0$ is equivalent to a standard GAN (unsupervised). Conversely, an SSL-GAN with the weights $w_u=0$ and $w_s=1$ specializes in classification. Finally, $w_u=0.5$ and $w_s=0.5$ is equivalent to the SSL-GAN in Eq. 5.

Lipi-SSL applies spatial diversity loss by assigning different values of w_u and w_s in each cell to preserve the diversity in the sub-populations. Communication between cells allows the best individuals to be trained with different loss weights. Using cells with varying loss functions fosters diversity and has been proven to enhance GAN training [15, 36]. Eq. 3 defines the weights, which are set according to the id i of the cell according to convex combinations. Figure 3 shows the different values applied to 2×2 (left) and 3×3 (right) grid layouts.

$$w_u = \frac{i}{N-1}, \quad w_s = 1 - w_u, \quad i \in [0, N) \quad (3)$$

Balanced labels batch sampler When sampling batches of data during training Lipi-SSL loads the image data batches and ensures that: (1) the same labeled data points in each batch are

Lipi-SSL source code is publicly available at <https://github.com/...>

Figure 3: Layout of a 2×2 and 3×3 grid with different loss weights w_u and w_s in the cells.

used throughout training (2) the classes of labeled data points are balanced equally.

Preliminary experiments have shown that the balanced labels batch sampler keeps diversity in the labeled training samples in the batches, which improves model training.

4.2 Lipi-SSL algorithm details

Lipi-SSL in Algorithm 1 starts by creating θ_B data batches for model training with the balanced labels batch sampler (L. 1). It then initiates parallel, asynchronous training on each cell by setting learning hyper-parameters (L. 3). In each cell, the training consists of T epochs. An epoch has three coevolutionary phases [15]: *sub-population update*, collecting neighborhood individuals; *SSL-GAN training* using Algorithm 2; and learning rate (λ) optimization by Gaussian mutation. After the training loop is complete, each cell constructs a generative model by learning an ensemble of generators, with mixture weights calculated using Evolutionary Strategies, L. 8. Note, the ensemble has fixed size n based on the topology of the neighborhood, invariant to the population size $|E|$ (method detailed in [15]). Then, for each sub-population of discriminators (classifiers), the classification score is computed by majority voting on the test dataset, L. 9. The quality score of the generated samples, e.g., inception score (IS), is computed for each generator ensemble, L. 10. The best sub-population of discriminators n_d^* and the best ensemble of generators $(n_g, \omega)^*$ regarding the computed scores are returned.

Algorithm 1 Lipi-SSL main steps

Input: T : Epochs, E : Cells, θ_B : Dataset, θ_R : Label ratio, θ_{COEV} : CoevSSLGAN params (Algorithm 2) θ_{ES} : ES params, λ : Initial LR, θ_{GM} : GM params
Return: n_d^* : neighborhood of generators, ω : mixture weights, n_d^* : neighborhood of discriminators,

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1:  $\theta_B \leftarrow \text{createBatches}(\theta_D, \theta_R)$   $\triangleright$  Create training batches
2: parfor  $k \in E$  do  $\triangleright$  Asynchronous parallel execution of all cells
3:    $n, \omega \leftarrow \text{initializeCell}(k, \theta_B)$   $\triangleright$  Initialization of cell
4:   for  $t \in [0, \dots, T]$   $\triangleright$  Iterate over epochs
5:      $n \leftarrow \text{copyNeighbours}(k)$   $\triangleright$  Collect neighbor cells
6:      $n \leftarrow \text{CoevSSLGAN}(n, \theta_B, \theta_{COEV}, \lambda)$   $\triangleright$  Coevolve SSL-GANs Algorithm 2
7:      $\lambda \leftarrow \text{updateLearningRate}(\lambda, \theta_{GM})$   $\triangleright$  Update learning rate
8:    $\omega \leftarrow \text{generatorEnsembleES}(\omega, n, \theta_{ES})$   $\triangleright$  Optimize generators ensemble
9:    $a_k \leftarrow \text{classificationScore}(n_d)$   $\triangleright$  Compute the classification accuracy
10:   $q_k \leftarrow \text{qualityScore}(n_g, \omega)$   $\triangleright$  Compute the generative quality score
11: end parfor
12: return  $n_d^*, (n_g, \omega)^*$   $\triangleright$  Best classifier and generator sub-populations

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Algorithm 2 CoevSSLGAN cell sub-population training in Lipi-SSL

Input: n : Neighborhood, θ_B : Batches, τ : Tournament size, λ : LR

Return: n : Neighborhood of trained sub-population

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1:  $B_r \leftarrow \text{getRandomBatch}(\theta_B)$   $\triangleright$  Random batch to evaluate GAN pairs
2:  $w_u, w_s \leftarrow \text{getLossWeights}(n)$   $\triangleright$  Loss weights  $w_u, w_s$  to compute  $\mathcal{L}_D$ 
3:  $\mathcal{L}_{G,D} \leftarrow \text{evaluate}(G, D, w_u, w_s, B_r)$   $\triangleright$  Evaluate sub-population, i.e., GAN pairs
4:  $g^*, d^* \leftarrow \text{select}(n, \tau)$   $\triangleright$  Tournament selection
5: for  $B \in \theta_B$  do  $\triangleright$  Loop over the batches in  $\theta_B$ 
6:    $d \leftarrow \text{getRandomOpponent}(D)$   $\triangleright$  Get random discriminator
7:    $g^* \leftarrow \text{updateNN}(g^*, d, B, \lambda)$   $\triangleright$  Update  $g^*$  with gradient
8:    $g \leftarrow \text{getRandomOpponent}(G)$   $\triangleright$  Get uniform random generator
9:    $d^* \leftarrow \text{updateNN}(d^*, g, w_u, w_s, B, \lambda)$   $\triangleright$  Update  $d^*$  with gradient and loss
10:   $G, D \leftarrow \text{updatePopulations}(G, D, g^*, d^*)$   $\triangleright$  Add  $g^*$  and  $d^*$ 
11:   $\mathcal{L}_{G,D} \leftarrow \text{evaluate}(G, D, w_u, w_s, B_r)$   $\triangleright$  Evaluate all GAN pairs
12:   $n \leftarrow \text{replace}(n, G, D)$   $\triangleright$  Replace the networks with worst loss
13:   $n \leftarrow \text{setCenter}(n)$   $\triangleright$  Set best generator and discriminator in center
14: return  $n$   $\triangleright$  Return cell neighborhood with trained sub-population

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Lipi-SSL applies competitive coevolution SSL GAN (CoevSSLGAN) in parallel at each cell in each epoch. The method starts with evaluating the sub-populations (*all-vs-all*). The fitness $\mathcal{L}_{g,d}$ of an individual is based on the loss functions, \mathcal{L}_G (generators) or \mathcal{L}_D (discriminators) with w_u and w_s . Next, the *best* generator g^* and discriminator d^* are selected (L. 1 to 4). The adversarial learning of g^* and d^* applies stochastic gradient descent against random adversaries (L. 5 to 9). Then, the trained g^* and d^* are included in the sub-populations. Finally, the *center* of the cell is replaced with the best loss (fitness) (L. 11 to 13).

Finally, each run of Lipi-SSL returns two models: (1) a classification model consisting of the sub-population of discriminators that have the best score n_d^* ; (2) a generative model consisting of the ensemble (sub-population) of generators $(n_g, \omega)^*$ with the best generated image quality score.

5 EXPERIMENTS

We describe the experimental setup and analysis.

5.1 Setup

We empirically assesses Lipi-SSL on MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets, considering both the classifier model accuracy and the quality of the images produced by the generative model. The classification accuracy is calculated by applying the classifier ensemble obtained by running Lipi-SSL on the test dataset. The generative models are evaluated on the generated image quality according to Inception Score (IS) [32] and Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [16].

Image datasets. We use two standard benchmark image datasets:

MNIST the Modified *National Institute of Standards and Technology* (MNIST) [19]. MNIST is a dataset of unbalanced handwritten digits (0 to 9) with a training set of 60 000 images and a test set of 10 000 images. Each image is 28×28 grey-scale pixels.

CIFAR-10 Canadian Institute For Advanced Research (CIFAR-10) [18] datasets. CIFAR-10 is a dataset of 50 000 training samples and 10 000 test samples of 32×32 color images of 10 object classes. The classes are: airplanes, birds, cars, cats, deer, dogs, frogs, horses, ships and trucks. CIFAR-10 is uniformly balanced.

Experiments. We investigate how to train a GAN for both classification accuracy and image generation quality with low-complexity

ANNs architecture. The two first rows in Table 1 summarize the experimental study for how much labeled data to use, the number of datasets investigated, the grid size, m (which determines the population size as m^2), complexity of GAN, measures of generated data quality, and training objectives. The other rows in the table show the experimental analysis of the state-of-the-art (SoA) SSL GAN methods used for comparison. Note, the SoA comparison is based on published results of classification accuracy and qualitative image samples. There were no quantitative image generation measures available in the published results.

Table 1: Overview of experimental setup based on tested datasets, number of tested datasets, grid size (Grid), measures of image quality from generator (Quality), complexity of GAN (Cplx.), and objectives (Obj.). Note, Ex. is qualitative evaluation of generated examples; M. is image quality measures e.g. IS, FID, TVD; C is classifier; Cls. is classification; and Both is classification and generation

Name	Tested datasets	Grid	Quality	Cplx.	Obj.
SSL-GAN [24]	MNIST, CIFAR	No	M.	G, D	Both
Lipi-SSL	MNIST, CIFAR	1, 2, 3	M., Ex	G, D	Both
FM-GAN [32]	MNIST, CIFAR	No	Ex	G, D	Cls.
MarginGAN [11]	MNIST	No	Ex	G, D, C	Cls.

Generator and discriminator deep neural network architectures. Lipi-SSL uses two variations of DCGAN architecture [31], that applies SX SSL-GAN loss, are used. A smaller variant of DCGAN tailored to MNIST images to reduce the model complexity and computational resources. Figure 10 in Appendix B shows the major details the SSL-DCGAN architecture used in the experimental analysis MNIST images are grey-scale so the SSL-DCGAN proposed has one input and output channel in the discriminator and generator. Another DCGAN architecture variant was used for CIFAR-10 dataset (see Figure 11 in Appendix B). The discriminator has two more layers and a smaller kernel size.

Lipi-SSL configuration parameters. The hyperparameters of Lipi-SSL are shown in Table 6 in Appendix C. Due to computational resource limitations, Lipi-SSL was tuned for 3×3. Note, the label rate was set in order to ensure that there were at least one labeled image per batch. After setting the parameters, a series of empirical parameter tuning experiments were performed to enhance the SSL GAN training, i.e., Instance Noise (IN) [34], Feature Matching (FM) [32], dropout [42], batch normalisation (BN) [44], and One-Sided Label Smoothing (OS-LS) [32]. Table 7 in Appendix C presents parameters used for Lipi-SSL.

Runtime environment. All the methods were written in Python3 and PyTorch. Our MNIST experiments used an HPC platform with IBM Power System AC922 (8335-GTG), Power9 architecture with 1TB RAM and 3.6GHz cores, and NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPUs with 32 GB RAM. For the CIFAR-10 we used a Google Cloud instance with 16 virtual CPUs each of which had 64GB memory and 4 Tesla T4 GPUs with 16GB memory each.

Lipi-SSL python source code is publicly available at <https://github.com/jamaltoutouh/lipi-ssl>

5.2 Experimental analysis

This section presents the results and the analyses of the proposed distributed Lipi-SSL training method on the MNIST and CIFAR-10 data sets. We present the classification accuracy and image generation of the trained models, the evolutionary learning process, and the comparison of Lipi-SSL against SSL-GAN (as a simple baseline) and SoA methods. Note, due to computational constraints different number of independent runs were performed for each data set. In addition, for SoA comparisons we cannot test the differences for statistical significance since only aggregate values were reported.

5.3 MNIST experimental results

For MNIST dataset 15 independent runs were performed for each configuration.

5.3.1 Classification accuracy with few labels. The key SSL challenge is to train the classifier with a small amount, 100 (0.0017) labeled samples, Table 2 summarizes the classification and image generation quality (FID) results by reporting the median, inter-quartile range (IQR), and best value of the distribution of the results for each grid size over 15 runs.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for classification accuracy and FID for experiments with 100 (0.0017) labeled images with Lipi-SSL for 15 independent runs. The best values are in bold, accuracy is maximized and FID is minimized.

Grid size	Accuracy (%) ↑			FID ↓		
	Median	IQR	Best	Median	IQR	Best
Lipi-SSL 1×1	85.54	16.87	93.13	11.87	10.34	5.92
Lipi-SSL 2×2	91.45	3.25	95.06	6.68	2.49	4.49
Lipi-SSL 3×3	96.27	0.72	96.99	4.34	2.15	3.36
Lipi-SSL 4×4	94.46	1.45	96.46	6.54	2.8	4.52

The results in Table 2 show that Lipi-SSL 3×3 provided the most competitive classifiers accuracy results. The classifiers with the highest accuracy were trained with this grid size (highest median and best values), showing robustness (lowest variation in results, i.e., smallest IQR). Apairwise statistical comparisons between Lipi-SSL 3×3 and the other grid sizes were performed by applying Wilcoxon statistical test. The results confirmed that Lipi-SSL 3×3 classifiers provide the best results with a statistical significance higher than 99% (i.e., p-value<0.01). The second-best classification accuracy is computed using Lipi-SSL 4×4 and has significantly better results than the other two grid sizes (i.e., p-value<0.01). This answers **RQ-1**, that an evolutionary GAN method can train both a high-accuracy classifier and a high-quality generative model.

Note that the best results were not obtained by the Lipi-SSL variant with the largest population (Lipi-SSL 4×4) but were produced by Lipi-SSL 3×3. This may be due to the sensitivity of the method to the hyperparameters. The algorithm parameter tuning experiments were carried out using a 3×3 grid.

5.3.2 Image generation quality with few labels. The results in Table 2 show that Lipi-SSL 3×3 generated the samples with the highest quality (lowest FID values) for all descriptive statistics considered. A pairwise statistical comparisons between Lipi-SSL 3×3

and the other grid sizes were performed by applying the Wilcoxon statistical test. This confirmed that Lipi-SSL 3×3 generative models provided the best FID results with a statistical significance higher than 99% (i.e., p-value<0.01). Figure 5f illustrates samples produced by the generative model trained by Lipi-SSL 3×3 with 100 labels. Furthermore, Lipi-SSL 4×4 and Lipi-SSL 2×2 trained the second best generators, respectively. However, there was no significant difference in the distributions of their FID results.

5.3.3 Classification accuracy sensitivity to number of labels. Table 3 presents the average classification accuracy and FID score for the classifiers and the generative models trained with SSL-GAN and Lipi-SSL with a varying number of labeled samples. Note that the fully unsupervised Lipizzaner has been included in the table to compare the generative models trained using labels (100 and 60 000 for Lipi-SSL) or not (0 for Lipizzaner). Lipizzaner has no accuracy results because it does not train classifiers but only generators. In addition, the SSL-GAN and Lipi-SSL 1×1 train a single generator-discriminator pair.

Table 3: Average (15 runs) accuracy and FID scores from different methods with 100 and 60 000 labeled images when applying semi-supervised learning, and 0 labels when using unsupervised learning. Best values are in bold, accuracy is maximized and FID is minimized.

Model & grid size	Labeled samples (Fraction)					
	0 (0)		100 (0.0017)		60 000 (1.0)	
	Acc.	FID	Acc.	FID	Acc.	FID
Lipizzaner 1×1	-	17.96	-	-	-	-
Lipizzaner 3×3	-	3.38	-	-	-	-
SSL-GAN	-	-	49.28%	403.39	84.10%	73.93
Lipi-SSL 1×1	-	-	86.03%	13.77	94.98%	8.94
Lipi-SSL 2×2	-	-	91.16%	7.02	99.14%	5.62
Lipi-SSL 3×3	-	-	95.96%	5.22	99.38%	2.72
Lipi-SSL 4×4	-	-	93.97%	7.13	99.29%	4.18

Table 3 shows higher classification accuracy when using more labeled data samples in the training dataset. Furthermore, the Lipi-SSL 1×1 accuracy was more competitive than the accuracy of the SSL-GAN, which implies that the learning rate optimization in Lipi-SSL method improves SSL.

For the Lipi-SSL variants with populations of generators and discriminators, i.e., grids larger than 1×1, the classification accuracies are higher than 90% when training with 100 samples. This demonstrates that Lipi-SSL can train accurate classifiers using datasets with only a some portion of the data labeled. The best classification accuracy is shown by Lipi-SSL 3×3 (95.96% and 99.38% when training with 100 and 60 000 labels), The second and third best ones are Lipi-SSL 4×4 and Lipi-SSL 2×2. These results confirm the trend observed in Table 2, i.e., Lipi-SSL 3×3 provides the best classifiers. This answers **RQ-2**, that higher quality samples can be generated from GANs with some labels (SSL) compared to no labels (unsupervised).

5.3.4 Image generation quality sensitivity to number of labels. Results in Table 3 show that the generative models trained with SSL GANs produce higher quality samples when using more labeled

data samples. In turn, the generative models trained with Lipi-SSL 1×1 provided better FID results than the generative models computed using SSL-GAN.

Comparing unsupervised learning (i.e., Lipizzaner) and SSL (i.e., Lipi-SSL), Lipi-SSL showed better FID results than Lipizzaner for the grid sizes studied. Moreover, for semi-supervised (Lipi-SSL) versus unsupervised (Lipizzaner) learning, better FID scores were obtained with Lipi-SSL using the whole dataset labeled (i.e., 60 000 labeled images). Thus, higher quality samples were generated when training GANs with SSL (with some labels) compared to unsupervised learning (without labels). Finally, when comparing the different Lipi-SSL grid sizes results improve with grid size (lower FID). However, Lipi-SSL 4×4 showed worse results than Lipi-SSL 3×3, as well as observed in classification accuracy results.

Comparing unsupervised learning (i.e., Lipizzaner) and SSL (i.e., Lipi-SSL), Lipi-SSL showed better FID results than Lipizzaner for the two grid sizes studied. Moreover, for semi-supervised (Lipi-SSL) versus unsupervised (Lipizzaner) learning, lower FID scores were obtained with Lipi-SSL using the whole dataset labeled (i.e., 60 000 labeled images). Thus, higher quality samples were generated when training GANs with SSL (with some labels) compared to unsupervised learning (without labels).

5.3.5 Lipi-SSL learning evolution. We examine the evolution of Lipi-SSL 3×3 model training regarding classification accuracy and image quality generation when using 100 labeled samples. Figure 4 illustrates the average classification accuracy and FID across different training epochs from the run with the median classification accuracy. Furthermore, Fig.5 displays the per-class accuracy over epochs 5, 50, and 100, along with an example of a generated image from these epochs.

Figure 4: Evolution over training epochs (x-axis) of accuracy (left y-axis) and FID (right y-axis) for MNIST using Lipi-SSL 3×3 with 100 labels. Accuracy is maximized and FID is minimized

Figure 4 of MNIST classification accuracy evolution shows a steep slope, indicating fast learning in the first generations. In the first five iterations, the average accuracy was already 85.04%. At this point, the highest accuracy was achieved for classes “0” and “6” with 97.76% and 94.09%, respectively (see Fig.5a). As training progressed, the slope flattened, and all classes had similar accuracy. The average classification accuracy at epoch 100 was 94.29% (see

Figure 5: Evolution of accuracies per MNIST class label and generated images as training progresses at different epochs for the median accuracy run with 100 labels for Lipi-SSL 3×3.

Fig.5c). The last 30 epochs are increasing and suggest that accuracy might not have converged.

Figure 4 shows that the evolution of FID behaves as a monotonically decreasing function with small oscillations. A sharp drop in the initial epochs conducted a considerable improvement in image quality between epochs 5 and 50 (see Figs.5d and 5e). Fig.4 reveals that after the first 40 epochs, the FID stabilized to a value lower than 10, as demonstrated by the improved image quality between epochs 50 and 100 (see Figs.5e and 5f).

5.3.6 Comparison with State-of-the-Art. We compare Lipi-SSL with the related state-of-the-art (SoA) methods in Table 1. Table 4 presents the classification accuracies results published by SoA and the ones computed by Lipi-SSL 3×3 for 100, 200, and 600 labeled samples. FM-GAN achieved the highest accuracy, over 99%, while MarginGAN had less competitive results, ranging from 96% to 97%. Lipi-SSL had slightly lower accuracy, ranging from 96% to 97%.

Table 4: Lipi-SSL vs. SoA classification accuracy on MNIST for varying number of labeled image samples.

Model	Labeled samples		
	100 (0.0017)	200 (0.003)	600 (0.01)
FM-GAN [32]	99.07%	99.10%	-
MarginGAN [11]	96.47%	96.97%	97.13%
Lipi-SSL 3×3	95.96%	96.07%	97.07%

One factor contributing to the differences in results is the complexity of the neural network models used, as shown in Table 1. The SoA methods use complex convolutional models with many layers and are trained for a longer duration (around 400 epochs or more). Moreover, the MarginGAN trains three models instead of only two. In contrast, Lipi-SSL achieved similar results with only 100 epochs and a 4-layer discriminator. This highlights that spatially distributed GAN training can enhance training efficacy,

overcoming a sub-optimal use of a less complex network architecture. These findings also align with similar studies on unsupervised GAN learning [12].

The SoA SSL methods prioritize maximizing the classification accuracy of the trained models. Whereas Lipi-SSL simultaneously optimizes the discriminative model (as a classifier) and the generative model (to produce high-quality samples). The authors of SoA methods do not measure the quality of the generated samples. As a result, only a qualitative comparison between SoA and Lipi-SSL is possible. Figure 6 shows images produced by the generators trained by SoA and Lipi-SSL for comparison purposes. Samples from FM-GAN and MarginGAN exhibit incomplete digits and poor visual quality. Lipi-SSL generates images of higher quality with a simpler GAN architecture.

Figure 6: Comparison of generated MNIST images by SoA methods and Lipi-SSL

5.4 CIFAR-10 experimental results

We present the experimental results on CIFAR-10 dataset for which seven independent runs were performed for each configuration.

5.4.1 CIFAR-10 classification accuracy. Table 5 reports the average accuracy classification and IS for the classifiers obtained using SSL-GAN and Lipi-SSL when varying the number of labeled samples used to train the models and grid sizes.

Table 5: Average (7 runs) classification accuracy and IS for varying number of labeled images considering Lipi-SSL and SSL-GAN. The best values for each number of labeled samples used are in bold, accuracy and IS are maximized.

Model & grid size	Number of labeled samples			
	5 000 (0.1)		50 000 (1.0)	
	Accuracy ↑	IS ↑	Accuracy ↑	IS ↑
SSL-GAN	59.26%	2.74	88.27%	-
Lipi-SSL 1×1	68.44%	3.64	95.47%	-
Lipi-SSL 2×2	74.79%	4.92	97.41%	-

Table 5 illustrates that increasing labeled samples in the training from 5 000 to 50 000 led to better accuracy results. For the CIFAR-10 dataset, Lipi-SSL 2×2 demonstrated the most competitive accuracy results. As shown for MNIST in Section 5.3.1, Lipi-SSL 1×1 showed significant improvement over SSL-GAN for CIFAR-10, emphasizing the benefits of Lipi-SSL’s training enhancements (regardless of the spatially distributed training).

5.4.2 CIFAR-10 image generation. The aim of Lipi-SSL is to train models to produce high-quality images and achieve a high classification accuracy level. The results in Table 5 show the average IS of Lipi-SSL and SSL-GAN on the CIFAR-10 dataset, using 5 000 labeled samples in seven independent runs. The generative models trained by SSL-GAN had the lowest IS, indicating lower image quality. In contrast, Lipi-SSL, which coevolves a population of generators and discriminators, produced better images (see Lipi-SSL 2×2 in Table 5).

5.4.3 CIFAR-10 Lipi-SSL learning evolution. This section discusses the evolution of the trained models regarding classification accuracy and IS for Lipi-SSL 2×2 with 5 000 labeled samples. The plot in Figure 7 displays the progression of the average classification accuracy and IS score throughout the training epochs for the run that provided the median classification accuracy. Both evaluated metrics start with a marked improvement during the first training epochs. Subsequently, the quality of both metrics shows steadier growth. Finally, it can be seen that the training has not converged at epoch 90, as the plots in the figure show an upward trend even at the later stages. The final classification accuracy for Lipi-SSL 2×2 was 74.8% at the end of the run, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Evolution of classification accuracy and IS for CIFAR-10 using Lipi-SSL 2×2. Accuracy and IS are maximized

Figure 8 illustrates the per-class accuracy at epochs 5, 45, and 90. The per-label classification accuracy for classes 2, 3, 4, and 5 improved more slowly than other classes, resulting in disparities in the classification accuracy, particularly during the early stages of training. At epoch 5, for instance, there is a significant difference between the accuracy for classes “5” and “9”, which were 36.28% and 71.73%. Although the differences were reduced as the training progressed, they still persisted. For example, at epoch 90, the accuracy for classes “5” and “9” were 71.04% and 87.26%.

5.4.4 Comparison with State-of-the-Art. We compare Lipi-SSL against SoA approaches. In addition, Figure 9 present samples generated by the generators trained by the compared methods. Note, MarginGAN was trained using 4 000 labeled samples. For 5 000 labeled samples, Lipi-SSL 2×2 got an accuracy of 74.79%, while the MarginGAN and FM-GAN had accuracies higher of 93.6% and 82.0%. The main findings from Figure 9 are consistent with the results obtained for MNIST in Section 5.3.6. We reiterate that Lipi-SSL

Figure 8: Evolution of accuracies for the CIFAR-10 class labels at some epochs for the median accuracy run with 5 000 labels for Lipi-SSL 2×2

uses simpler models, with fewer neural networks and neurons, and trains for fewer epochs, as shown in Tables 1 and 6. For context, with the entire labeled dataset, Lipi-SSL 2×2 had an accuracy of 97.41%. Finally, Lipi-SSL trains a generative model that produces good quality image samples.

Figure 9: Comparison of generated CIFAR-10 images by various State-of-the-Art methods and Lipi-SSL

6 CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

Our main objectives (RQs 1-2) were to achieve good performances, for both classification and image generation, using a simple architecture, low training duration, and few labeled samples. We demonstrated that a spatial evolutionary GAN for semi-supervised learning method, Lipi-SSL, can provide this. Lipi-SSL generated samples of good quality when training with few labels (semi-supervised) compared to training without labels (unsupervised).

The coevolutionary approach of Lipi-SSL injects diversity into the GAN training which can improve the performance. In addition, Lipi-SSL uses optimisations such as Feature Matching and Instance Noise to stabilize the training. We evaluated our approach on the MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets and achieve good classification and the images generated by our models are of good quality, visually comparable to state-of-the-art approaches. Note, that the compared approaches did not provide quantitative measures of the image quality, so the potentially more biased visual inspection must be used. Furthermore, Lipi-SSL behaves as expected from previous work, e.g. with an increasing grid size can increase performance of the image generation [12, 15]. Moreover, in [12], a distributed evolutionary GAN is limited by the ANN architecture, so we expect that Lipi-SSL

can improve with more complex the GAN architectures, e.g. the ones used in SoA.

Finally, the diversity of the generators and discriminators and loss functions has been demonstrated to have impact on the performance of Lipizzaner [12, 15]. Future work will investigate how the diversity of the supervised and unsupervised loss weights in the grid contributes to the performance improvement. Further, future work is also to investigate more configurations, datasets, e.g. TinyImageNet and STL-10, and architectures, as well as the coevolutionary dynamics of Lipi-SSL. Moreover, the comparisons can be run with the same computational budgets.

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A SOFTMAX-BASED SSL-GAN

The GANs in Lipi-SSL are trained by using the simple softmax-based SSL. SSL-GAN is built on a standard unsupervised GAN by providing another task to the discriminator, classifying the real labeled images it receives as input. As a result, the loss of a SSL-GAN discriminator requires a new supervised loss term. The generator’s loss is unchanged from a standard GAN (see Eq. 4). While the discriminator’s loss in Eq. 5 is defined according to an unsupervised component for fake and unlabeled real images (\mathcal{L}_{Du}), and a supervised component for labeled real images (\mathcal{L}_{Ds}).

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_u(u)} [\phi(1 - D_v(G(z)))] \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_D = \mathcal{L}_{Du} + \mathcal{L}_{Ds} \quad (5)$$

In SSL, images from the real distribution are classified into K classes. Softmax SSL-GAN aims to train a discriminator to learn to classify real and fake samples and, simultaneously, distinguish the real samples among the K classes. The classification problem is extended by adding a $(K+1)^{th}$ class to label fake samples. Therefore, the discriminator is trained to label real data from 1 to K (according to the sample class) and fake data as $K+1$.

When the discriminator is trained with real labeled data, i.e., $(x, y) \sim G_*$, it computes the supervised loss aimed at identifying the correct label for the data as a general supervised classifier does. The \mathcal{L}_{Ds} loss function is defined in Eq. 6.

$$\mathcal{L}_{Ds} = \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim G_*(x)} [\phi(p(y|x); y < K + 1)] \quad (6)$$

The \mathcal{L}_{Du} loss in Eq. 7 is applied to train a discriminator with fake or unlabeled data. The first component focuses on real data. The term $\mathbb{E}_{x \sim G_*(x)} [\phi(D_v(x))]$ is computed as the sum of the first K outputs of the softmax layer corresponding to the real classes and returns the probability of the sample being real. The second component enforces the discriminator to predict fake images as $K + 1$.

$$\mathcal{L}_{Du} = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim G_*(x)} [\phi(D_v(x))] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_u(u)} [\phi(y = K + 1 | G(z))] \quad (7)$$

The pseudocode in Algorithm 3 summarizes the SSL-GAN training. Lines from 4 to 7 present the steps applied to train the discriminator d . Lines from 8 to 11 illustrate the steps to train the generator g , which are the same ones performed in unsupervised learning.

Algorithm 3 SSL-GAN training

Input: T : Epochs, θ_D : Dataset, B_s : Batch size, λ : Learning rate

Return: g, d : Trained generator and discriminator

```

1:  $g, d \leftarrow \text{initializeNetworks}()$   $\triangleright$  Initialize generator and discriminator
2: for  $t$  do  $\in [0, \dots, T]$   $\triangleright$  Loop over the  $T$  training epochs
3:   for  $B \in \theta_D$  do  $\triangleright$  Loop over the batches in  $\theta_D$ 
4:      $z \leftarrow \text{getRandomNoise}(B_s)$   $\triangleright$  Get random generator input
5:      $X_f \leftarrow \text{generateImages}(g, z)$   $\triangleright$  Compute  $G(z)$  to generate images
6:      $\mathcal{L}_D \leftarrow \text{getDiscriminatorLoss}(d, B, X_f)$   $\triangleright$  Compute  $\mathcal{L}_D$  (Eq. 5)
7:      $d \leftarrow \text{gradientDescent}(d, \mathcal{L}_D, \lambda)$   $\triangleright$  Update parameters of  $d$ 
8:      $z \leftarrow \text{getRandomNoise}(B_s)$   $\triangleright$  Get random generator input
9:      $X_f \leftarrow \text{generateImages}(g, z)$   $\triangleright$  Compute  $G(z)$  to generate images
10:     $\mathcal{L}_G \leftarrow \text{generatorLoss}(g, X_f)$   $\triangleright$  Compute  $\mathcal{L}_G$  (Eq. 4)
11:     $g \leftarrow \text{gradientDescent}(g, \mathcal{L}_G, \lambda)$   $\triangleright$  Update parameters of  $g$ 
12: return  $g, d$   $\triangleright$  Return trained  $g$  and  $d$ 

```

B NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURES FOR LIPI-SSL EXPERIMENTS

Figures 10 and 11 illustrate the architectures defined to perform the experimental analysis of Lipi-SSL on MNIST and CIFAR-10, respectively. In these two figures, Conv2d [28] and ConvTranspose2d [29] refer to the PyTorch implementations of layers for a convolutional operator and a two-dimensional transposed convolutional operator, respectively.

Figure 10: Proposed SSL-DCGAN architecture to deal with MNIST (with PyTorch layers).

C LIPI-SSL CONFIGURATION SETUP

Table 6 outlines the coevolutionary settings and the details of the network architectures for both datasets considered, MNIST and CIFAR. Important training settings include the batch size, the label rate, and the initial learning rates (LR) of the generator and discriminator. Note, the label rate was set in order to ensure that there were at least one labeled image per batch.

Figure 11: Proposed SSL-DCGAN architecture to deal with CIFAR (with PyTorch layers).

Table 6: Configurations for the Lipi-SSL method used in the experiments

Parameter	MNIST	CIFAR-10
<i>Network topology</i>		
Network type	MNIST SSL-DCGAN	CIFAR SSL-DCGAN
Input neurons to generator	100	100
Discriminator hidden layers	4	7
Generator hidden layers	4	5
Neurons per hidden layer	16 384 - 131 072	16 384 - 262 144
Network complexity	128	64
Generator output neurons	128×28×28	64×64×64
Activation function	<i>tanh</i>	<i>tanh</i>
<i>Training settings</i>		
Batch size	300, 400, 600	250, 200
Label rates (in batch size order)	0.01, 0.005, 0.00167	0.08, 0.1
<i>Coevolutionary settings</i>		
Stop condition	100 training epochs	90 training epochs
Tournament size	2	2
Grid sizes	1×1, 2×2 and 3×3	1×1 and 2×2
Generator Performance measure	FID	Inception Score (IS)
<i>Hyperparameter mutation</i>		
Optimizer	Adam	Adam
Initial discriminator LR	0.001	0.0007
Initial generator LR	0.0002	0.0003

After setting the parameters in Table 6, a series of empirical parameter tuning experiments were performed to configure IN, FM, dropout, batch normalisation, and OS-LS (see Table 7).

Table 7: SSL-GAN parameter settings. IN is instance noise

Parameter	MNIST	CIFAR-10
IN mean	0.0	0.0
IN initial standard deviation	0.1	0.7
IN standard deviation decay rate	0.0005/iteration	0.0005/iteration
IN standard deviation decay limit	0.065	None
Dropout	No	Yes
Batch normalization	Yes	Yes
Positive label smoothing value	0.9	0.9

D FURTHER EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS RESULTS

Tables 8 and 9 summarize the main experimental results. These two tables present the classification accuracy, image generation quality (in terms of FID for MNIST and in terms of IS for CIFAR-10) and image generation diversity (TVD) results by reporting the minimum, median, inter-quartile range (IQR), and maximum of the distribution of the results for each grid size. The MNIST results were computed over 15 independent runs, while the CIFAR-10 results were obtained over 7 independent runs.

Table 8: Accuracy, FID, and TVD scores using different models with 100 and 50 000 labelled data points when applying semi-supervised learning and 0 labels when using unsupervised learning (averaged across 15 runs). Best values are in bold, accuracy is maximized, and FID and TVD is minimized.

Model & grid size	Labeled samples (Fraction)								
	0 (0)			100 (0.0017)			50 000 (0.83)		
	Acc.	FID	TVD	Acc.	FID	TVD	Acc.	FID	TVD
Lipizzaner 1×1	-	17.96	0.10	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lipizzaner 3×3	-	3.38	0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-
SSL-GAN	-	-	-	49.28%	403.39	0.16	84.10%	73.93	0.14
Lipi-SSL 1×1	-	-	-	86.03%	13.77	0.08	94.98%	8.94	0.07
Lipi-SSL 2×2	-	-	-	91.16%	7.02	0.07	99.14%	5.62	0.06
Lipi-SSL 3×3	-	-	-	95.96%	5.22	0.07	99.38%	2.72	0.04

Table 9: Classification accuracy using varying number of labelled data points considering Lipi-SSL and SSL-GAN, averaged across 7 runs. The best values for each number of labeled samples used are in bold, accuracy and IS are maximized, and TVD is minimized.

Model & grid size	Number of labeled samples					
	5 000 (0.1)			50 000 (1.0)		
	Acc.	IS	TVD	Acc.	IS	TVD
SSL-GAN	59.26%	2.74	0.081	88.27%	-	-
Lipi-SSL 1×1	68.44%	3.64	0.043	95.47%	-	-
Lipi-SSL 2×2	74.79%	4.92	0.031	97.41%	-	-